

OLIGOMER COUPLING AGENTS FOR PHOSPHATE BASED GLASS FIBRE/PLA COMPOSITES

P. Haque^{a*}, A. J. Parsons^a, I. Ahmed^a, D. J. Irvine^{a,b}, G. S. Walker^a, C. D. Rudd^a

^a Faculty of Engineering, University of Nottingham, Nottingham, NG7 2RD, UK

^b School of Chemistry, University of Nottingham, Nottingham, NG7 2RD, UK

*E-mail: eaph2@nottingham.ac.uk

SUMMARY

Poly(lactic acid) (PLA) oligomers as coupling agents have shown higher interfacial shear strength in phosphate based glass fibre/ PLA composites. To influence bonding on the glass fibre surface, short chain PLA oligomers with different end groups were used as coupling agents. Mechanical properties of the sized fibres/PLA composites were found to be increased.

Keywords: Phosphate glass fibre, PLA, coupling agent, mechanical properties and bioabsorbable composites.

INTRODUCTION

Bioabsorbable phosphate glass fibre/polymer composites are being investigated as alternatives to commonly used metal alloy-based bone fracture fixation devices. According to Knowles [1], these 'Third Generation' implants remain in the body for the short term necessary for mechanical stabilisation of tissue. In addition the degradation products of the bioabsorbable implants perform an active function in the tissue regeneration process. A bioabsorbable fracture plate could potentially transfer load to the healing bone gradually over time.

Among bioabsorbable polymers, polyhydroxy acids and especially poly(lactic acid) (PLA) are well known for a number of biomedical applications; sutures, pins, screws, drug delivery systems and scaffolds for use in tissue engineering applications [2]. Hydrolytic degradation, or complete mass loss of PLA takes approximately 12 to 16 months [3]. PLA degrades to form lactic acid which is normally present in the body [4]. The reported elastic modulus of PLA ranged from 0.6 to 4 GPa which is higher compared to the familiar bioabsorbable polyhydroxy acids such as polycaprolactone, polydioxanone [5]. However, the elastic modulus of bone ranges from 6 to 20 GPa, which is much higher than that of the polymers. Therefore, reinforcement of the polymer has been considered to attain sufficient mechanical properties for fracture fixation [5].

Phosphate based glasses (PBG) have great potential to be used as reinforcement in absorbable composites for bone implants. PBG show a complete and congruent degradation in aqueous media with zero order release of incorporated oxides [6]. The chemical composition of PBG can be designed to closely match that of the inorganic phase of bone [7]. Moreover, the composition of PBG can be easily tailored giving variation in mechanical, thermal and biological properties to suit the end application.

The major limitation of PBG fibre reinforced polymer composites encountered thus far is rapid strength loss after exposure to an aqueous physiological environment [8]. Recent research on glass fibres has involved surface treatments and coupling agents to try and enhance the hydrolytic stability of the fibre-polymer interface [9, 10]. Apart from silane, modified oligomers/macromers of the matrix materials have currently been investigated to improve the interfacial bonding between fibre and matrix. Phosphate glass fibres (PGF) coated with a mixture of modified methacrylate macromer and HEMA, in the same macromer matrix gave the composite a bending strength of around 115 MPa [11]. However, the fibres used were 125 μm in diameter, which would have made them weaker and less flexible due to their large size, and therefore not appropriate as reinforcing fibres. Polyacrylic acid (PAA) and glycidyl acrylate modified PAA coupling agents have been applied to E-glass fibres and ESCA (electron spectroscopy for chemical analysis) studies showed broad and shifted C_{1s} peak at 288.5 eV (O-C=O) suggesting adhesion of polymers to the fibre surface [12].

The present study was conducted in order to investigate the effects of different PLA oligomer coupling agents on PGF/PLA composites.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Phosphate Glass and Fibre Production

PGF were produced by melt-draw spinning of phosphate glass (composition $40\text{P}_2\text{O}_5$ - 24MgO - 16CaO - $16\text{Na}_2\text{O}$ - $4\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ in mol%) using a dedicated in-house fibre manufacturing facility and then annealed at 474°C [13]. The fibres were kept in a desiccator prior to use. These fibres are designated as P40 fibres for the remainder of this paper. Annealed and untreated P40 fibres were used as control for the study. The mechanical properties of PGF produced fluctuate slightly from batch to batch due to their variation in diameter and severity of surface flaws. Due to this slight variation, the properties of control and sized fibres were compared using fibres produced from within the same batch. Two batches of P40 fibres produced were named as control-1 and control-2.

PLA Oligomer Synthesis

Acid ended PLA (PLA-acid) and its sodium salt (PLA-Na) were synthesised by ring opening polymerisation of D, L lactide (Sigma Aldrich, U.K.) and the resulting products were used without further purification. Ethylene glycol, glycerol and sorbitol (Sigma Aldrich, U.K.) ended short chain PLA oligomers were also produced and named as EG-PLA, G-PLA and S-PLA respectively, synthesised by degrading Natureworks PLA (PLA- grade 3051D, Natureworks LLC, U.S.A) using a tin catalyst. A further short chain sorbitol ended PLA (S-PLA-1) of lower molecular weight compared to S-PLA was also synthesised in the same way in order to investigate the effect of molecular weight on the mechanical properties of sized fibres. The resulting EG-PLA, G-PLA and S-PLA and S-PLA-1 oligomers were then dissolved in dichloromethane (Sigma Aldrich, U.K.) and precipitated in methanol (Sigma Aldrich, U.K.) to purify the polymers. The precipitates were then dried under vacuum.

Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC)

The number average molecular weight (Mn) and polydispersity index (PDI) of the oligomers were determined using Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC). GPC was performed utilising a refractive index (RI) detector with HPLC grade tetrahydrofuran (Fisher Scientific, U.K.) as the eluent. Analysis was performed at 40°C with a flow rate of 1 mL/min through two PLgel Mixed-C columns with a calibration range of 2000 – 5000 Da calibrated with poly(styrene) narrow standards. All GPC equipment and standards were supplied by Polymer Laboratories (Varian Inc). GPC data was analysed using the Cirrus GPC Offline software package.

Coupling/Sizing Agent Application Process

The fibres were sized with the above PLA oligomers (6 oligomers) and 3-aminopropyl triethoxy silane (silane) (Sigma Aldrich, U.K.). Using a dip-coating process, the agents were applied to the P40 fibres with a fibre:solution ratio of 1.5g:100ml and a sizing agent:solvent ratio of 0.0043moles:100ml [13]. This was followed by heat curing and finally rinsing with the sizing solvents to remove any residual artefacts. Chloroform and ethanol/water (90:10 v/v ratio) were the sizing solvents for the PLA oligomers and silane respectively. PLA-acid, PLA-Na and silane sized fibres were then Soxhlet extracted for 24 hrs in chloroform to ensure complete removal of any residual artefacts.

Single Fibre Tensile Test (SFTT)

The tensile properties of the fibres produced were obtained by single filament testing using a Series S Hounsfield machine, following the international standard BS ISO 11566 [14]. PGF are essentially brittle and Weibull distribution is an accepted statistical tool used to characterise the failure mode of brittle fibres. In this study, Weibull parameters were obtained from the tensile strength data calculated using Minitab® 15 (version 3.2.1).

Interfacial Shear Strength (IFSS) Studies

The IFSS was measured from single fibre composites (SFC) by using the single fibre fragmentation method. SFC specimens were produced by placing an axially aligned single fibre between two rectangular pieces of PLA film [13] of 80 x 20 x 0.4 mm³ and hot pressing at 210°C with a 2.5 kg weight for 1 minute. The resulting specimens were cooled to room temperature and finally cut into dog-bone shapes. These were axially loaded in a tensile testing machine (Hounsfield series S testing, U.K.) with a load cell of 1kN and crosshead speed of 1mm/min. All IFSS values were obtained from an average of 5-10 repeat specimens. After having conducted the tensile tests, the specimens were placed under an optical microscope (Nikon Optiphot, Japan) and the numbers of fibre fragments present in the 25mm gauge length were tallied, in order to calculate the IFSS.

These IFSS values obtained were calculated using the Kelly-Tyson equation below [15];

$$\tau_i = d \cdot \sigma_f / 2L_c \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

where τ_i is the IFSS, d is the fibre diameter, σ_f is the single fibre tensile strength at the critical fragment length L_c .

$$\sigma_f = \sigma_o (L_c / L_0)^{-1/m} \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

$$L_c = 4/3(L_f) \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

$$L_f = L_0/N \quad (\text{Equation 4})$$

where σ_0 and m are the Weibull scale and shape parameter respectively, for the fibre strength at gauge length L_0 , L_f is the average fragment length and N is the number of fibre fragments obtained from the SFC tests [16].

Statistical Analysis

A t-test was conducted to identify whether there were statistically significant differences between the means of the two sets of data [17]. The statistical analysis of the uncorrected and corrected IFSS values was performed using a paired t-test. The statistical analysis of the tensile strength and IFSS values of the fibres and SFC was conducted using a two sample unpaired t-test. To interpret the t-test results, a two tailed P-value (P) was considered with a 95% confidence interval and the value of significance level 0.05. The difference was accepted as significant when P obtained was less than 0.05.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The IFSS values obtained for all the sized, Soxhlet extracted and the control-1 fibres are summarised in Table 1. All the values were calculated using a 2-parameter Weibull model for the control-1 fibres. The Weibull scale and shape parameters of the control-1 fibres obtained were 340.0 and 6.3 respectively (Figure 1a). The IFSS obtained for the control-1 fibres was 8.9 MPa. The highest IFSS value of 13.3 MPa was obtained for PLA-Na (Mn ~ 2233 Da, PDI ~ 2) sized specimens. Silane and PLA-acid (Mn ~ 1419 Da, PDI ~ 2) treated fibres showed IFSS close to those of control-1 and PLA-Na sized fibres respectively.

It is observed from Table 1 that the IFSS values of PLA-acid and PLA-Na sized fibres were higher than that of the control-1. The low molecular weight PLA-acid and PLA-Na coupling agents showed relatively high IFSS values (i.e. improved bonding), which was suggested to be due to similarities in the chemical structures of the agent and matrix. The PLA-Na showed better bonding between the fibre surface and matrix as compared to the PLA-acid. The processing used and the relatively high level of hydrolytic instability of PLA-acid may result in it decomposing during preparation of the test specimens. However, the IFSS value of the silane treated fibre was similar to that of the control-1. A similar result was also obtained by Cozien-Cazuc et al. for both unsized and silane sized $P_{40}Na_{20}Ca_{16}Mg_{24}$ PBG fibres within a PCL matrix [18].

The strength profile of the PLA-Na sized fibres was investigated in order to verify if their Weibull parameters were different to that of control-1. The Weibull scale and shape parameters obtained for PLA-Na sized fibres were 419.5 and 5.8 respectively (Figure 1b), which were different from those of control-1 (Figure 1a). The IFSS value of PLA-Na sized fibres was therefore corrected using the Weibull parameters of the PLA-Na sized fibres in order to obtain more accurate results. After correction, the IFSS value obtained was 17.2 MPa. It was observed that the change in IFSS with and without correction of the Weibull parameters was statistically significant ($P < 0.0001$) for the PLA-Na sized fibres.

Figure 2 shows the tensile strength and modulus of the different functionalized PLA oligomer sized and control-2 fibres along with the Mn of the oligomers. The tensile strengths of control-2 and PLA-3, PLA-4 and PLA-5 sized fibres were 321.1 ± 93.3 , 355.9 ± 82.9 , 327.4 ± 81.0 and 339.6 ± 108.6 MPa respectively. The tensile modulus values of control-2 and PLA-3, PLA-4 and PLA-5 sized fibres were 74.0 ± 7.3 , 81.0 ± 5.6 , 75.1 ± 6.2 , 77.0 ± 5.8 GPa respectively. The Mn of PLA-3, PLA-4 and PLA-5 obtained using GPC were around 8210, 1217 and 2881 Da respectively. The PDI of the functionalized oligomers obtained was approximately 3. However, the difference between the tensile strength and modulus of all the sized fibres was found to be statistically insignificant in comparison to control-2.

Figure-3 shows the IFSS values of control-2 and EG-PLA, G-PLA and S-PLA sized fibres within a PLA matrix, tested to evaluate the effect of the end-group choice of these low molecular weight oligomer coupling agents. These IFSS values were calculated using the individual Weibull parameters of control-2 and each of the sized fibres. The IFSS of control-2 and EG-PLA, G-PLA and S-PLA sized fibres obtained were 14.3 ± 6.1 , 8.9 ± 2.6 , 16.5 ± 3.3 and 23.2 ± 10.3 MPa respectively. The IFSS of EG-PLA and S-PLA (P values are 0.019 and 0.017 respectively) were significantly different from that of control-2. The highest IFSS value was obtained from S-PLA sized fibres followed by G-PLA and EG-PLA. The polymer chain end of S-PLA contains 5 hydroxyl groups which is higher than that for G-PLA (2 hydroxyl groups) and EG-PLA (1 hydroxyl group). The interfacial reactions were expected to be either between the hydroxyl groups on the PGF surface and the coupling agents and/or formation of salt complexes with the metal cations present in the glass. Regarding the interfacial reactions, the number of hydroxyl groups in the oligomers is assumed to influence the IFSS values.

Comparing Figure 2 and 3, it is observed that the Mn of PLA oligomers influenced the mechanical properties of the sized fibres whilst no trend was observed in the level of interfacial adhesion with a difference in their Mn. The increase in chain length of the agents is suggested to contribute to an increase in coverage of the flawed surface of the fibres. However, the functional end groups of these oligomer chains play a vital role in their ability to effectively bond to the PGF surface. The differences in the end groups of the oligomers perhaps negate any effect Mn may have on the IFSS values of the sized fibres.

To understand the effect of Mn of a particular oligomer on the mechanical and interfacial properties of the sized fibres, two oligomers having the same functional end group with variation in chain length were investigated. Another sorbitol ended PLA; S-PLA-1 of Mn~115 Da was introduced to make this comparison. In Figure 4, the mechanical properties and the IFSS value of these sized fibres were compared with that of the S-PLA (Mn ~ 2881 Da). The tensile strength and modulus of S-PLA-1 sized fibres obtained were 279.4 MPa and 73.8 GPa respectively, which were lower than that of S-PLA sized fibres. However, taking statistical variation into account, no difference was observed in tensile properties of S-PLA and S-PLA-1 sized fibres. The IFSS value of 9 ± 3.5 MPa was obtained for S-PLA-1 sized fibres. The IFSS values obtained for S-PLA and S-PLA-1 sized fibres were significantly different (P = 0.0002).

With the functional end group for S-PLA and S-PLA-1 being the same, the affinity toward the PGF surface was expected to be similar for both these oligomers. The matrix-philic tails of the oligomers being different in length may have shown variation

in the level of affinity with the PLA matrix. S-PLA-1 having very low Mn, the chain length of the agent was not sufficient to afford significant number of interactions and/or entanglement with the matrix for achieving good interfacial adhesion. Therefore, the longer chain length (i.e. higher Mn) was seen to confer a higher shear strength value of around 23 MPa for the sized fibres.

CONCLUSION

The PLA oligomer coupling agents being similar in chemical structure to the matrix showed a better quality of interfacial bonding between PGF and the PLA matrix. The functional end groups with a greater number of hydroxyl groups showed better compatibility (or attachment) toward PGF. With regards to the number of hydroxyl groups present in the oligomers, sorbitol ended PLA showed the highest IFSS. It was also observed that the molecular weight of an oligomer had a substantial effect on the interfacial properties of the sized PGF fibres. An optimum size of PLA chain with a suitable functional end group is suggested to be a hugely beneficial coupling agent for the PGF/PLA composites investigated.

Table 1: IFSS of control-1 and silane, PLA-acid and PLA-Na sized, Soxhlet extracted fibres

Sizing agents	Control-1	silane	PLA-acid	PLA-Na
IFSS values (MPa)	8.9 ± 2.9	8.4 ± 2.1	12 ± 2.3	13.3 ± 2.3

(a) Weibull analysis of control-1 fibres

(b) Weibull analysis of PLA-Na sized fibres

Figure 1: Weibull analysis of (a) control-1 and (b) PLA-Na sized, Soxhlet extracted fibres were completed from the tensile strength data calculated using Minitab® 15 (version 3.2.1).

Figure 2: Tensile properties of control-2 and EG-PLA, G-PLA and S-PLA sized fibres: effect of molecular weight of PLA oligomers.

Figure 3: IFSS values of control-2 and EG-PLA, G-PLA and S-PLA sized fibres

Figure 4: Effect of molecular weight of S-PLA and S-PLA-1 on the tensile and interfacial properties of sized fibres.

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